

Designing the Ion Gate of a Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometer

Adam Furman under the supervision of **Dr. Derek Stein**, Brown University

Abstract

The Stein lab is developing a time-of-flight mass spectrometer (TOF-MS) to determine whether a nanopore ion source can emit amino acids directly into high vacuum without also producing charged droplets. A crucial component of the spectrometer is the ion gate, which blocks the flow of ions into the spectrometer's flight chamber until the measurement begins. This thesis describes the design of the ion gate. First, a simulation framework is created to model how two proposed gate designs interact with ions. The simulation framework is tested to ensure its physical accuracy, and then is used to determine the minimum voltage necessary to open and close the ion gate. A parallel plate deflection-based gate design is chosen because it requires less voltage to operate than a mesh-based design. Calculations are carried out to determine the gate's impact on the accuracy of the mass spectrometer, and the impact is found to be minimal based on both the size of the gate and its electrical properties. The gate is designed was created in 3D modelling software and fabricated by a machine shop. The gate is then cleaned and mounted onto the assembly of the mass spectrometer. Experimental data shows that the gate functions as expected, and that the voltage required to operate it conforms to the results of the simulations.

Table of Contents

<u>Abstract</u>	1
<u>Introduction</u>	3
<u>Background and Motivation</u>	6
<u>The Simulation Framework</u>	13
<u>Verifying Simulated Physics</u>	19
<u>Analysis of Designs and Relevant Physics</u>	23
<u>Simulated Experiments</u>	29
<u>Designing the Physical Ion Gate</u>	36
<u>Integrating the Ion Gate</u>	40
<u>Testing the Ion Gate</u>	42
<u>Summary and Conclusion</u>	45
<u>References</u>	46
<u>Acknowledgements</u>	48
<u>Appendix: Selected Code for Simulations</u>	49

Introduction

Proteins are highly complex organic molecules that are present in all known forms of life and are essential to survival. They compose around 30% of the substance of living things, and perform complex actions, such as carrying oxygen to cells or breaking down ingested food into usable molecules (Koshland). An understanding of the composition and behavior of proteins is at the core of several scientific fields, with special relevance in medicine and biology.

What classifies a molecule as a protein is its composition. Proteins are made of amino acids, which are organic molecules containing an amine group ($-NH_2$), bonded together in a long chain by peptide bonds. The sequence of the amino acids shapes the protein and determines how it functions (Koshland). The chain-like nature of a protein means that sequencing it – determining the order of the amino acids that make it up – identifies the protein and predicts its function. Protein sequencing is similar to DNA sequencing, as both procedures involve identifying the components of a long biopolymer. But proteins consist of sequences of twenty different amino acids, in contrast to DNA, which only has four nucleotides, which makes sequencing proteins more difficult.

The first method of protein sequencing was a technique known as Edman degradation. This is a chemical procedure, which involves sequentially breaking apart the bonds between amino acids and then using secondary reactions to determine the presence or absence of each amino acid. The sequence of the protein is established by carefully hydrolyzing only one bond at a time, but this task becomes more and more difficult the longer the protein is, limiting the length of a determinable sequence to around thirty amino acids (Koshland). This length limit of Edman degradation constrains the complexity of proteins that can be successfully analyzed, and yet the process is also highly resource and time intensive. An improved process would have no length restriction and be more efficient to carry out.

Mass spectrometry has become the primary method of protein analysis and sequencing and has improved on the restrictions of Edman degradation. A mass spectrometer, given a charged particle, uses the properties of its flight through an electromagnetic field to determine its mass to charge ratio (Brown). Since mass to charge ratios are all known for amino acids, the output of a mass spectrometer can distinguish between them. Steen and Mann describe how a mass spectrometer fits into the sequencing process: first, the peptide bonds are broken, and then the solution containing the amino acids is pumped through an electrospray nozzle, which is a

type of ion source which disperses the solution into a plume of charged droplets, carrying the ions inside them (2). The droplets in the beam undergo Coulomb explosions due to the electromagnetic forces between the ions inside them, which split the droplets up until isolated (bare) ions emerge. The bare ions are then passed into a mass spectrometer, which determines which amino acid is present (Drachman et al.).

However, the electrospray ion source is not well suited to protein sequencing. Since it produces droplets which must split apart many times before producing bare ions, which can only then be introduced into the mass spectrometer, the combination of erratic ion trajectories following Coulomb explosions and collisions with the parts of the instrument that connect the nozzle to the spectrometer result in only around 1% of the amino acids reaching the spectrometer. Thus, building an accurate sequence can require billions of sample proteins, so that the failures of the electrospray nozzle can be compensated for statistically (Drachman et al.).

The Stein lab at Brown University is developing a new type of ion source that seeks to improve on the traditional electrospray nozzle by reducing the required amount of sample proteins and moving towards single-protein sequencing. This novel ion source, called a nanopore ion source, is theoretically capable of emitting bare ions directly into vacuum, without accompanying charged droplets. This is enabled by the extremely small (nanoscale) size of the tip of the nozzle, at which the surface tension of the solution is high enough to allow ions to be pulled through by a potential difference without the solution spraying out in droplets as well. In the proposed approach, to sequence a protein, it is first fed through an extremely narrow tube, where the peptide bonds are broken. Then, each amino acid comes to the tip of the nanopore, where it is extracted into the vacuum and passed into the mass spectrometer, which determines the protein's identity and its location within the sequence (Drachman et al.). The nanopore ion source would be housed directly in the vacuum, which means ions are not lost during the transfer into the vacuum chamber, and no Coulomb explosions take place if no droplets are present. Thus, the nanopore approach has the potential to sequence even single protein molecules instead of requiring billions of samples (Drachman et al.).

Confirming that the nanopore ion source delivers ions but not droplets is a crucial step in developing it as a component in a protein sequencing method. Verifying that no droplets are produced means that the detected signal of droplets and ions, which differ in mass by several orders of magnitude, needs to be filtered out separately. Under such filtering, if no droplet-mass

signal is found, and an ion-mass signal appears consistently, the nanopore ion source is functioning as hypothesized. Otherwise, the occurrence and behavior of droplets can be studied to potentially decrease their frequency or mitigate their impact on the mass measurements.

Time-of-flight mass spectrometry has been used to measure the relative fraction of droplets and ions emitted by ion sources (Gamero-Castaño and Cisqueña-Serra). Unlike a magnetic sector mass spectrometer, which uses a magnetic field to deflect the path of charged particles in an arc that depends on their mass to charge ratio, a time-of-flight mass spectrometer measures how long it takes charged particles with a particular kinetic energy to travel through a chamber of known length. The particles are accelerated to a set kinetic energy using an electric field, then let into the flight chamber by the ion gate. Particles of different masses have different final velocities after being accelerated to the same energy, and thus take different amounts of time to cross the flight chamber. By placing a detector at the far end of the chamber, the time at which each particle is detected can be used to compute the particle's mass to charge ratio.

The timing of the entry of the ions into the chamber is critical. Since the mass measurement depends on the time difference between entering the flight chamber and hitting the detector, there needs to be a means of specifying the moment when ions enter the chamber. This is the function of a gate – when it is closed, ions cannot enter the flight chamber, and when it is opened, the clock starts. To fulfill its role in the experiment, the gate must conform to strict design requirements. First, it has to open and close at microsecond speeds, which implies that it must be electric in nature, not mechanical. Second, its dimensions must be small enough to both fit inside the spectrometer assembly and not introduce significant uncertainty into the time measurements. Finally, it cannot block a significant portion of the ions when it is open. These requirements can be summarized as high speed, compact dimension, and high transmission.

This thesis describes the process of conceiving, simulating, designing, and testing such an ion gate. It describes in greater detail the background information and considerations relevant to the design. Then, it details the process of constructing a computer simulation framework capable of modeling the flight paths of ions through the gate (as well as arbitrary charge configurations). The simulation framework is used to compare and evaluate gate designs, from which a final candidate is selected. Then, the gate is modeled in computer design software. Finally, the physical parts are assembled, cleaned, and installed in the spectrometer assembly and tested to verify that the gate functions as intended.

Background and Motivation

As described in the introduction, a time-of-flight mass spectrometer relies on accelerating particles linearly and measuring the time it takes them to traverse the length of the detector (“Mass Analyzer - Time of Flight”). A simplified schematic a time-of-flight spectrometer is shown below in Figure 1.

Figure 1: A schematic of a time-of-flight mass spectrometer, where an ion is introduced at the ion source, accelerated using an electric potential, let into the flight chamber by the ion gate, and detected as a current signal at the far end.

Once particles are introduced into the spectrometer via the ion source, they are accelerated by means of an electric field. An electrostatic barrier – the ion gate – holds particles back from entering the flight chamber of the spectrometer until the start of measurement, when the gate is opened, and the particles can enter the flight chamber. They coast through the flight chamber until they hit a detector at the far end. The velocity of the particles after acceleration is inversely proportional to their mass, and thus the time of flight between the detector and barrier is directly proportional to mass to charge ratio, which can be found using the formula

$$\frac{m}{q} = \frac{2K_0 t^2}{s^2} \quad (1)$$

where $\frac{m}{q}$ is the particle mass to charge ratio, K_0 is the known kinetic energy, t is the measured flight time, and s is the distance traveled by the particle, that is, the length of the flight chamber.

Equation 1 is used by a time-of-flight mass spectrometer to compute the mass to charge ratio of a particle. The path length is fixed at the length of the flight chamber (plus or minus uncertainty caused by the size of the gate), and the initial kinetic energy is determined by the potential difference between the ion source and extractor electrode. The time is measured by the spectrometer – hence the time-of-flight designation – thus allowing for the mass to be computed, given that the charge is known. In a 30cm flight chamber at an energy of 500eV for a particle with a charge of +1, a measured time of 5 μ s corresponds to a mass of approximately 8amu.

A time-of-flight mass spectrometer can measure a large range of masses as compared to other types of spectrometers (“Mass Analyzer - Time of Flight”). This property is crucial to testing the nanopore ion source extraction mechanism. What distinguishes the nanopore ion source is its ability to extract ions directly from solution to vacuum, without also producing an enclosing droplet of solution around the ion. This distinguishes it from the more conventional electrospray nozzle used as an ion source (Drachman et al.).

Figure 2: Left¹ - An electrospray nozzle producing a cone of droplets, not bare ions. Right² - A diagram of the nanopore ion source, showing a scan of the tip and bare ions being pulled from solution to vacuum by a potential difference.

A nanopore can theoretically produce bare ions and no droplets, but this has not yet been experimentally confirmed (Drachman et al.) It is necessary to test that no droplets are present in the beam that results from the nanopore. The experiment that seeks to confirm the absence of droplets is set up as follows: First, sodium (Na^+) ions are dissolved in solution, which is fed through a thin tube towards the nanopore. Then, a potential difference is created between the nanopore and the extractor electrode (see Figure 2 – Right), which pulls the ions out of the solution and into the vacuum. Then, the ions are let into the mass spectrometer by the ion gate and their mass determined by measuring their time of flight across the flight chamber. However, it is possible that the nanopore could produce droplets as well as bare ions.

To confirm the extraction of only bare ions, our instrument must be able to detect both droplets and bare ions within a single measurement session. We estimate the range of mass to charge ratios of interest to be able to interpret experimental results. A single sodium ion has a mass of 3.8×10^{-26} kg and a charge of +1. The diameter of a droplet is presumably related to

¹ Image: Fernandez de la Mora, “*The Fluid Dynamics of Taylor Cones.*”

² Image: Drachman et al.

the size of the nanopore tip, in this case roughly 50nm (see Figure 2 – Right) and a drop of that size would contain roughly 6×10^6 water molecules and have a mass of 6.5×10^{-17} kg. The charge of a droplet is determined by the Raleigh limit (Taflin et al.), which gives the maximal charge of a droplet of a given radius as

$$q^2 = 64\pi^2\gamma r^3 \quad (2)$$

where q is the charge, γ is the surface tension of the liquid, and r is the droplet radius.

For water droplets with a surface tension of $\gamma = 0.0728 \text{ N/m}$ and a radius of 25nm, the resulting charge is $q = 8.47 \times 10^{-7} \text{ C}$, thus their mass to charge ratio is 8.67×10^{-11} .

Therefore, the necessary range of mass to charge ratios is on the order of 10^{15} . A time-of-flight mass spectrometer is capable of detecting ions at both ends of this mass range (“Mass Analyzer - Time of Flight”), and so it can be used to verify the absence of droplets and presence of ions.

Figure 3 shows a diagram of the Stein lab spectrometer, modeled after similar designs by Gamero-Castaño and Cisquella-Serra.

Figure 3: A labeled schematic of the proposed time-of-flight mass spectrometer.

The journey of an ion through the instrument begins at the bottom, as the solution is pumped through the feed line into the vacuum chamber which encompasses the whole spectrometer. At the nanopore ion source, ions are forced into the narrow tip. The ion source is set at a given potential by a power supply. The extractor is an electrode which generates a potential difference

between the ion source and itself, causing the ions to be pulled into the flight chamber of the spectrometer if the ion gate is open. The beam of particles then travels across the flight chamber until it hits the detector at the far end.

Figure 4³: Shows the current vs. time plot for an electro spray nozzle as recorded in a mass spectrometer by Gamero-Castaño and Cisquella-Serra, with steps in the detected current for both ions and droplets.

Figure 4 shows the results of previous time of flight measurements performed by Gamero-Castaño and Cisquella-Serra. The detector in the mass spectrometer records current over time, and two distinct “steps” in are seen. The first step (“ions” in the figure) corresponds to bare ions, which cross the flight chamber at very high velocity due to their low mass. The second step, which occurs at a later time (“droplets” in the figure), corresponds to droplets of various sizes. Droplet sizes can vary, so the step is spread out over a range of times corresponding to a range of droplet masses. However, it is clear that there are two categories of object being detected. A successful test of the nanopore ion source would show no second step for droplets, and only the first step for ions.

The most crucial component of the spectrometer, which enables time-of-flight measurements, is the ion gate. The gate must stop ions from passing through when active, and open and close on a time scale smaller than the time resolution needed to measure the masses of different ions and be permeable to particles when deactivated. The gate must also fit into the assembly of the mass spectrometer, which already contains electrostatic components that focus and aim the beam of ions that is extracted from the nanopore.

³ Image: Gamero-Castaño and Cisquella-Serra, “*Electrosprays of highly conducting liquids.*”

Ions leave the source at a velocity that can be determined using

$$E = qV = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 \quad (3)$$

where m and q are the mass and charge of the particle accelerated through a potential difference V , to a final velocity v .

A calculation shows that the resulting velocities are much too fast to be able to use a mechanical gate. After being extracted from the nanopore, the ions have an energy between 300 and 500eV depending on the voltage difference between the nanopore and extractor. For a sodium ion, as used in the testing and verification experiments, with a mass of 3.81×10^{-26} kg, the resulting velocity range is between 50,000 and 65,000 m/s. Thus, the fastest ions would cross the 30cm flight chamber in 15 μ s.

The gate must also be small enough to not cause a significant error in the spectrometer's mass resolution. The uncertainty in the length of the path traveled caused by the gate can be at most the linear size of the gate along the direction of the ion beam. The uncertainty in mass to charge ratio can then be found by propagating the error according to the formulas

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta s &= l_{gate} \\ \Delta s^2 &= 2s(\Delta s) \\ \Delta \frac{1}{s^2} &= \frac{\Delta s^2}{s^2} = \frac{2\Delta s}{s} \\ \Delta \frac{m}{q} &= 2K_0 t^2 \left(\Delta \frac{1}{s^2} \right) = \frac{4K_0 t^2 l_{gate}}{l_{chamber}} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where s is the flight path length, l_{gate} is the length of the ion gate, K_0 is the energy of the ion, t is the time of flight measured by the spectrometer, and $l_{chamber}$ is the length of the flight chamber.

To distinguish between individual ions, the mass resolution must be extremely high, on the order of 10^{-27} kg. In the case of the sodium ion beam used for testing, where ions have a mass of 3.81×10^{-26} kg, a charge of $q = +1$, and a velocity of up to 65,000 m/s and take only 5 μ s to cross a 30cm chamber, the resulting upper bound on l_{gate} to maintain the 10^{-27} kg accuracy in mass is 0.037m, that is, the gate should not be more than around three and a half centimeters long along the direction of the ion beam. This is a reasonable size constraint and corresponds well to the space available within the spectrometer, which is around 3cm. The

constraint to be able to distinguish between droplets and ions is much less stringent, given the large discrepancy in mass to charge ratio between droplets and ions.

Within these theoretical considerations, two types of gate designs were explored over the course of this project. The first type consists of three meshes, shown in Figure 5, and is similar to the gate developed by Szumlas et al.

Figure 5: Schematic of the mesh gate design. Ions travel from left to right, encountering the grounded mesh and then the positively charged mesh.

The outer two meshes are grounded to prevent the electric fields inside the gate from interfering with other parts of the spectrometer, such as the extraction potential or the ion beam focusing optics. To close the gate, the middle mesh is set to a positive (or negative, depending on the charge of the ions being used) voltage. Ions are then stopped by the electric field of the middle mesh. To open the gate, the middle mesh is grounded, allowing the ions to pass through without any electric field to influence them. However, some ions may still hit the meshes themselves.

The second type of gate design that was based on the idea of deflecting, not stopping the ions. This deflection gate (Figure 6) is set up like a parallel plate capacitor.

Figure 6: Schematic of the deflection gate, showing the grounded box (black), and the positive (blue) and negative (red) charged plates. Ions travel through the opening from left to right.

In this design, the gate is prevented from interfering with the rest of the ion optics by having the electric field confined by a grounded box. Ions enter the box and exit the box through a circular hole in either side. Inside the box are two plates, set up like a large parallel-plate capacitor. To close the gate, a potential difference is created between the two plates. To open the gate, both

plates are grounded. Depending on the voltage applied to the plates, the ion beam can be trapped inside the box entirely – deflected so much that the ions collide with either the side of the box or one of the charged plates – or just aimed away from their original trajectory so that they do not strike the detector at the far end of the flight chamber.

To evaluate these designs and study their behavior without having to build physical models, a computer simulation framework needed to be developed to understand the behavior of ions as they pass through each of these gates.

The Simulation Framework

The simulation framework designed to model the gate designs was intended to be robust and extensible. Therefore, it was constructed in parts, across several different simulation libraries. Each library handles a different task in the simulation process. The libraries were then utilized from Jupyter Python notebooks to create simulated experiments and view the outputs.

The first component of the framework is a Gauss-Seidel solver for electrostatic potential in three-dimensional space, with electric field computation and mapping between experimental units and simulation points. The Gauss-Seidel solver is in the first half of `libem.py`. The second component is an equation of motion solver for charged particles given an electric field, with collision detection and extrapolation of the electric field from nearby simulation points, which is based on a modified Runge-Kutta method. The equation of motion solver is in the second half `libem.py`. The third component is collection of simulated basic objects, such as boxes, meshes, and cylinders for use in constructing boundary conditions. The boundary condition models are in `components.py`. The final component is a collection of visualization functions for displaying electric potential, field, and motion data in two and three dimensions. The visualization tools are stored in `libvis.py`.

The entire codebase for the simulation framework as well as the experiments can be found on a GitHub repository⁴. In addition, the Appendix contains selected code for critical parts of the simulation framework. The rest of this section describes the structure of the simulation framework, the mathematical background for the electrostatic simulations, and demonstrates some of the framework's basic features by providing sample graphics.

The Simulation Space

All the modeling done by this framework happens within a Simulation Space, which represents the experimental setup in three-dimensional space. Its primary function is to store information about the electrostatic potential, electric field, and physical objects included in the simulation. The simulation space is divided into discrete lattice points, which correspond to entries in a NumPy array. Computations of the electric potential and field are accomplished on this same lattice. The governing variable that determines the size and accuracy of the simulation

⁴ <https://github.com/furmada/TOFSim>

space is the scale, that is, the number of lattice points per each linear unit. For example, at a scale of 20, a simulation space of size $1 \times 1 \times 1$ simulation unit would contain $20 \times 20 \times 20 = 8000$ lattice points in a three-dimensional cube. The actual density of lattice points will be chosen by finding the minimum density at which the physics of the simulation matches real-world physics.

To compute the electrostatic potential, we used a custom Python implementation of a three-dimensional Gauss-Seidel method. A visual aid for the mathematics behind this method is given in Figure 7.

Figure 7: An illustration of the Gauss-Seidel method. The value at the central lattice point is computed as the average of the neighboring lattice points.

Starting from the boundary conditions, the Gauss-Seidel method is used to compute the value of the potential at every point in the simulation lattice. This is an iterative way of solving Laplace's equation in free space, shown below.

$$\nabla^2 V = 0 \quad (5)$$

The solutions to this Equation 5 have the property that their value at any point is equal to the average of the values at neighboring points (Robertson). This means that the value of the potential at each lattice point can be computed by summing its neighboring lattice points.

The iterative process for implementing the Gauss-Seidel method is as follows. For each iteration, the boundary conditions are first imposed. This means that a certain configuration of lattice points, corresponding to the design of the gate, is kept at a constant potential. Then, each lattice point is assigned a new value of the potential by summing over its neighbors. Finally, the difference between the new and old values is computed. This difference represents the convergence of the solution – as more iterations are carried out, the average difference goes to zero as the actual solution for the potential is found.

Once the average difference drops below a specified level or the program exceeds a maximum iteration limit, the Gauss-Seidel solver terminates. After the potential has been computed, the negative gradient of the potential is taken at each location of the lattice to yield the

electric field. The results of a simulation can be saved to a file for rapid reuse without the need to redo the same computation.

In addition to the electric potential and field, the simulation space also stores information about which boundary conditions correspond to solid objects. This is to aid in the simulation of particle trajectories, as described in the next section.

The Particle Motion Solver

The dynamics part of the simulation computes the trajectories of charged particles within the simulation space. At the core of this process is second order differential equation solver for Newton's law, which has been modified from the standard form found in scientific Python libraries to function well with sudden changes in the direction of the velocity as particles interact with solid objects.

To compute the electrostatic force on a given particle, the program identifies the closest points on the simulation lattice and then computes an inverse distance weighted average. The closer the particle is to a simulation point, the closer the electric field value is to the field value at the lattice point. To save computation time and preserve local features in the field, only the nearest 27 lattice points (the nearest point and one step in the positive and negative direction along each axis) to the particle are considered. A schematic of how this weighting procedure is shown, simplified into two dimensions and four nearby lattice points, in Figure 8.

Figure 8: A schematic of how the electric field is computed at the location of the particle by averaging the values at nearby lattice points. Closer points are weighted more heavily.

Once the value of the electric field at the particle's location is obtained, the electrostatic force is applied to the particle, as well as gravity, which can be enabled along any axis.

The differential equation of motion is integrated using the `solve_ivp` method in the `scipy` package. This method allows for a high degree of precision using an 8th-order Runge-Kutta method, as well as control features useful for the implementation of collision detection. Specifically, the minimum and maximum time step sizes are set based on the scale of the simulation, ensuring that more than one lattice point cannot be traveled by the particle in a single step of the equation solver. This ensures that any sharper features of the electric field are obeyed, as well as improves the ability of the solver to detect collisions with walls.

A collision with walls is detected by examining the next step along the particle's path at each iteration of the differential equation solving algorithm. If the next step along the current velocity trajectory results in the particle entering a lattice point marked as solid, a collision is detected. In such a case, the differential equation solver terminates, and the "bounce" velocity is computed by flipping the direction of the velocity along each axis which is blocked by the wall. A coefficient can also be passed to represent the ratio of energy lost by the particle when it hits a wall – 1 representing a fully elastic collision. In the case of fully inelastic collisions, the solver terminates immediately once the wall is hit. The differential equation solver is then restarted at the same location, but with the bounce velocity as the new initial velocity. This approach has the useful property of preserving high accuracy for the particle's overall trajectory while preserving the sharp discontinuities caused by hitting walls.

Object Modeling

The physical objects in the simulation, including the mesh, box, and parallel plates, are modeled as boundary conditions for the Gauss-Seidel solver. In general, each type of object first converts from simulation units to lattice coordinates, then imposes a fixed voltage on those coordinates.

For arbitrary or curved objects, it is also possible to provide an array with the dimensions of the lattice which acts as a mask, setting the voltage for every nonzero point in the mask array. Boundary conditions are compounded together before being passed to the simulation object by the `make_enforcer` method. Each boundary condition can also be specified as solid or not solid, changing whether particles will bounce off the object.

The `components.py` library file contains a collection of basic objects that can be assembled to make more complex models. Several such components are passed as boundary conditions at once to model each gate design.

Visualization Tools

The data generated by the simulation framework can be displayed visually by a large collection of tools collected in the visualization library. Graphs can be overlaid to show several different types of information at once. Notably, the potential, electric field, and particle trajectories can all be displayed in two and three dimensions, with two dimensional cross sections along any axis at any location.

Figures 9 and 10 below offer a sample of the visualizations included with the library.

Figure 9: Output from the visualization library showing a two-dimensional cross-section of a ring, with the potential intensity in blue. Equipotential curves are labeled, and electric field vectors are shown at each simulation lattice point.

Figure 10: Output from the visualization library showing a three-dimensional model of a mesh set to a nonzero voltage relative to ground, with the potential shaded blue.

In addition, the visualization tools include methods for showing particle trajectories over time, as well as for making video animations. Visualizations play a key part in the design process for the ion gate, as they allow there to be intuitive correspondence between what is simulated and the computer design software (and ultimately, the real assembled gate).

Verifying Simulated Physics

To prove that the simulation software can be used to accurately model gate design, virtual experiments needed to be performed to show that the simulation gave physically accurate results. This was done by modeling simple, well-known scenarios for which the behavior of the electric fields and moving particles are well known and can be easily verified using the visualization tools. Note that all image scales and units are in internal simulation units, and do not yet correspond to real-world measurements. The purpose of verification is to show that these internal units form a system with consistent physics.

The Parallel Plate Capacitor

The first simple scenario modeled was a parallel-plate capacitor. In this system, it is known that the voltage between two plates with opposite charges equal in magnitude decreases linearly along the direction from the positive to the negative plate, while the electric field in that direction remains constant.

Figure 11: A visualization showing a simulated parallel plane capacitor, with blue (positive) and red (negative) values of the potential shaded.

By graphing the potential along an x axis cross-section, the linear slope of the potential and the constant value of the electric field are used to confirm that the simulation conforms to the known solution of a parallel plate capacitor. The simulation was repeated at varying densities of simulated points (scales) to verify the value of the potential is independent of the scale, which is a crucial indicator that the simulation suite works as intended. However, higher scale factors are

expected to show smoother electric fields, as more points are available to generate a numerical derivative from.

Figure 12: Potential and E_x field along a cross-section of the parallel-plate capacitor simulation.

The results also show that the values of the electric field near the simulation boundary can be unpredictable, however in the region of interest between the plates the results are highly consistent with theory. Note the linear descent between -0.5 and $+0.5$ on the x axis.

Particle Free Flight

The correct behavior of the differential equation solver for particle motion was verified by testing it on the motion of particles in free space. In this experiment, a cohort of 100 particles, with normally distributed masses, charges, and initial velocities was generated and placed in a simulated space with no electric potential. The particles' motion was then solved, and distance traveled recorded by summing over the steps of the computation. The result was then compared to the theoretical prediction of $d = vt$ based on the initial velocity of each particle. This experiment was meant to confirm that the solver gives results that are independent of mass and charge in free space, a prerequisite for correct behavior in an electric field.

Figure 13: The difference between theoretical and traveled distance for simulated particles traveling in free space. Note that the blue and orange lines overlap exactly.

In all cases, the difference between the expected and traveled distance was zero, showing that Newton's laws hold in free space for the simulator.

Retarding Potential

The third test case was the equivalence of translational kinetic energy and potential energy in the form of voltage. This equality is known as retarding potential, and can be written in the form

$$V = qK_0 \quad (6)$$

where q is the charge of the particle and K_0 is the kinetic energy.

In the simulated scenario, a particle is generated with $K_0 = 0.5$ in simulation units and $q = 1$. A solid charged plate is also modeled, and collision detection is turned off to verify that the potential alone can stop the particle. The particle then moves towards the plate and is slowed by the field. It is expected that the behavior of the particle will more closely match theoretical predictions as the simulation scale increases, since more lattice points can better approximate a continuous electric field. The minimum scale that produces physically correct results will then be used to ensure more complex simulations are behaving accurately.

Figure 14: Cross-section views of the particle's trajectory (green) along the x, y, and z axes as well as force components as the particle approaches plate held at a potential equivalent to its kinetic energy, at a simulation scale of 25.

Running the scenario for varying scales and voltages, the theoretical behavior is confirmed, as the particle is successfully stopped using a voltage ($V = 0.5$) corresponding to its energy. At scales at or above 25, this happens reliably. However, the particle is not stopped at some lower scales, corresponding to an electric field that is not sufficiently smooth enough to well approximate a continuous function. In addition, tracking the force experienced by the particle over time confirms that the force is in the correct direction and grows in magnitude as the particle approaches the plate. This experiment shows that a scale of 25 lattice points per simulation unit is a recommended minimum for obtaining physically accurate results.

Analysis of Designs and Relevant Physics

We evaluated the competing ion gate designs using simulated experiments, but it was also necessary to consider other factors to when developing each design. First and foremost, there are performance factors relating to how quickly the gate can be opened and closed as well as how much uncertainty it causes in mass measurements. Second, there are electrical considerations, which include the voltage needed to operate the gate, as well as the gate's electrical properties, such as capacitance and time constant when operating as part of a circuit. Third, there are engineering considerations, which relate to the practicality and feasibility of constructing the gate within the design parameters of the rest of the spectrometer. All these categories need to be addressed in the process of choosing a final gate design.

The Mesh Design

The three-mesh design was the first design considered. As previously shown in Figure 6, it consists of three conductive meshes, aligned one after the other perpendicular to the path of the ion beam. Similar gate designs exist in the literature: Szumlas et al. utilize a wire-array ion gate for the purposes of ion-mobility spectroscopy. Their gate is constructed by first fabricating a plastic frame, onto which a wire is then threaded.

Figure 15: The prototype wire gate design from Szumlas et al. The wire diameter is 0.127mm, and the outer gray portion is constructed out of plastic. The four holes are for mounting. Szumlas et al. report that the gate can handle up to 500V for short periods of time, and that it performed well when tested. However, their experimental needs are different than the needs of this experiment. Nonetheless, the previous implementation of such a design suggests that a

mesh-based approach should at least be considered. Using three meshes in a linear “stack” instead of just one means that the electric field of the middle mesh can be limited to the region bounded by the two outer meshes. This prevents the gate’s electric field from interfering with the rest of the ion optics, next to which it is located.

Calculations and simulations can be done to determine the performance factors of the gate. The first concern with a design which lies physically in the path of the ion beam is that of the transmission rate, that is, what fraction of the beam will hit the gate, even if the gate is open (that is, the middle mesh grounded). The permeability P of a mesh can be determined based on the thickness of its wires and the spacing between them using

$$P = \frac{2d}{s} \quad (7a)$$

where d is the diameter of the mesh’s wires, and the spacing between the wires is s . The wires run in both the horizontal and vertical direction, hence the factor of two.

The ideal permeability is over 90%, which for wires the same diameter as those used by Szumlas et al. corresponds to a spacing of 0.28mm. This is not infeasible to construct, and indeed, meshes with comparable permeabilities exist as standard components in machine shops. Nonetheless, even a high permeability still means some ions will be blocked by the gate. This is seen in simulated experiments as well. Furthermore, stacking three gates and requiring 90% permeability through all three at once changes the equation to:

$$\sqrt[3]{P} = \frac{2d}{s} \quad (7b)$$

The modified requirement still results in manageable sizes, but nonetheless needs to be considered when considering the mesh design.

The electrical properties of this design also need to be considered. One such critical behavior of the gate is how it affects the ion beam as it opens – when the voltage decreases from a high potential to ground, allowing the ions to begin passing through. During this transitional period, the beam could potentially be deflected or unfocused. A simulated experiment, discussed in the next section, will study this. Likewise, simulated experiments can verify the applied voltage necessary to stop a beam of ions with a given energy. Since the mesh is fairly dense, its behavior should be well approximated by that of a solid plate, however verifying this is necessary. Excessively high operating voltages are undesirable, as they require special

experimental equipment. In addition, there is also the concern of degradation over time, as ions colliding with the mesh will cause damage to the wires and eventually require replacement.

The practical dimensions of the gate can also be determined using the simulation. The key variable here is the space between the meshes along the direction of the ion beam. In the ideal model of a time-of-flight mass spectrometer, the gate is infinitesimally thin, meaning that the ions do not spend any time flying through the gate itself – when the gate is opened, they immediately enter the flight chamber. But this is not the case with the mesh design, or indeed with any other physical gate. Once the gate is open, the ions must first traverse the length of the gate before entering the flight chamber. Opening the gate does not happen instantaneously, and an ion may be located somewhere within the bounds of the gate when the electric field is switched off. This means that there is uncertainty in the length of the path traveled by the ion caused by the size of the gate. As described in Equation 4, this places a constraint on the size of the gate along the direction of travel of the ions. However, the limit of roughly 3cm does not pose an issue for this design, since the three meshes are more than thin enough to place within the size constraint.

The mesh can also be simulated with relative ease using the simulation suite. Figure 10 shows a three-dimensional rendering of the electric field generated by a mesh as modeled by the software. In summary, the mesh design is a good first candidate. However, simulations are needed to test its electrical properties and find the voltage required to close the gate.

The Deflection Design

The second design considered was the deflection gate, as shown previously in Figure 6. The key insight motivating this design is the fact that closing the gate need not necessarily imply stopping the particles from entering the flight chamber. This is because it is the signal of current over time produced by the detector that yields mass measurements, and it is this signal that needs to be turned on or off by means of the gate. The detector is a physical target, a Faraday cup – a device which uses its geometry to catch incoming ions and prevent them from exiting, thereby generating a current from the ions hitting its walls – which in the case of this experiment has a diameter of only 2cm. Therefore, to turn off the signal, it is sufficient to simply deflect the beam away from the Faraday cup.

This deflection can be achieved by a gate configuration resembling a parallel plate capacitor. The design consists of a box, with a hole at either end along the axis of the ion beam. The box is grounded to prevent the interior electric field from interfering with the rest of the spectrometer, and to absorb any ions which collide with the interior of the box. Two charged plates are placed parallel to the axis of the ion beam. To close the gate, a voltage is applied to the plates, creating an electric field between them. Ions that pass through will be deflected towards one of the plates depending on the sign of their charge. This gives them a velocity in the direction perpendicular to their previous axis of travel, and if this velocity is large enough, it will cause the ions to miss the Faraday cup on the far end of the flight chamber.

The magnitude of the velocity in the perpendicular direction necessary to deflect the ion is given by the relation

$$v_{\perp} = \frac{rv_{\parallel}}{s} \quad (8)$$

where v_{\perp} and v_{\parallel} are the velocities of the ion perpendicular to and parallel to the axis of the beam, r is the desired deflection radius, and s is the length of the flight chamber. For a sodium ion with a velocity of $65,000 \text{ m/s}$, a Faraday cup with a radius of 1 cm , and a flight chamber of length 30 cm , the minimum required perpendicular velocity is 2166 m/s , or better put, the ratio of perpendicular to parallel velocity is $1/30$. A simulated experiment will be used to determine the voltage required to impose this velocity on the ions.

The deflector gate is subject to the same physical design constraints as the mesh gate. It must fit within 3 cm on the axis of the ion beam both for assembly and error purposes. In addition, because the gate is placed behind the extractor and ion optics, it should accommodate a beam of about 1 cm diameter, since this is the size of the path through the ion optics. Therefore, the box of the gate should be around $3 \times 2 \times 2 \text{ cm}$ in size to bring the parallel plates as close to the beam's path as possible without physically blocking it.

Because this gate resembles a parallel plate capacitor, it is also important to consider its electrical properties as part of a circuit. The gate will be connected to a voltage source, which will be turned on to close the gate. A capacitor in a system that includes resistance induces a time constant which factors into the speed at which the gate can open and close. It is necessary to compute the capacitance and time constant for the gate. The capacitance can be computed using the standard formula for a parallel plate capacitor

$$C = \frac{k\epsilon_0 A}{d} \quad (9)$$

where the permittivity $k = 1$ for a vacuum, A is the area of the deflection plate, and the distance between the plates is d .

Given the size constraints of the gate, referencing the final design as described in the section “Designing the Ion Gate,” the area of the plates as built is 380mm^2 with a separation of 13mm . The capacitance is then 0.259pF . Taking an upper bound of $1\text{k}\Omega$ for the resistance of the wires connecting the gate to the voltage source, the time constant for this RC system is $\tau = 0.26\text{ns}$, which is practically instantaneous – the potential difference on the gate will respond in less than $1/5000^{\text{th}}$ of the flight time of the ions across the flight chamber. Therefore, the electrical properties of the deflection gate are favorable for its use in the mass spectrometer.

The deflection gate can also be modelled with the simulation suite. It is simplified to exclude minor features such as screws, and it is represented as shown in Figure 16 below.

Figure 16: Three-dimensional and cross section view of the solid simulated deflection gate. Sections are taken along the x , y , and z axis in order. The x axis is the axis of the ion beam.

The dark red and blue rectangles in Figure 16 are the parallel plates (see Figure 6). Note the holes that allow the ion beam to pass through the gate along x axis. This model is used during simulated experiments.

The deflection gate has several distinct advantages when compared to the mesh gate. It does not physically sit in the path of the ion beam, and thus has a 100% transmission rate. There are no fine components that can be damaged over time by repeated collisions with ions. And, because the ions only need to be deflected and not fully stopped in their direction of motion, it is likely that the required voltage to operate the gate will be much lower than the mesh design. For these reasons, the deflection gate was the design chosen to be built and installed.

Simulated Experiments

Two simulated experiments were conducted for each gate design. The experiments were designed to answer two questions about the behavior of the gate. First, and most importantly, it was necessary to find the operating voltage of the gate. The operating voltage is the voltage that needs to be applied to the gate to stop an ion of a certain energy. The efficiency of the gate can be evaluated by computing the ratio of operating voltage to ion energy V/qK_0 , which can be called the energy ratio of the gate. The smaller the energy ratio, the more efficient the gate, the better the design, as high voltages are undesirable as they require specialized instruments to switch on and off quickly. The second experiment sought to characterize the behavior of the ion beam as it passes through the gate at various voltages. The opening or closing of the gate does not happen instantaneously, and during this intermediate period of rising or falling voltage, the ion beam will be affected but not fully blocked. Understanding this response and seeing whether it results in any kind of focusing or defocusing of the beam may be necessary for the interpretation of experimental results. This experiment also characterizes the transmission rate of the gate, that is, what fraction of the ions pass through the gate when it is closed.

The Operating Voltage Experiment

This experiment is framed as an optimization problem, with the goal of finding the minimum voltage that must be applied to the gate to “close” it to an ion of a given energy. The setup for such an experiment is straightforward. First, the gate is modeled at a sufficient scale to accurately represent the resulting electric fields. Then, a simulated particle representing the ion is introduced into the simulation, traveling along the direction of the ion beam. The energy of the simulated ion is fixed at a given K_0 . The simulation framework is then used to compute the flight path of the ion through the model of the gate over a time interval long enough to allow it to fully cross the region of the gate if unimpeded, calculated as $t = \frac{\sqrt{2mK_0}}{s}$ where s is the length of the simulated space along the direction of travel of the ions.

This type of minimization problem lends itself well to a root-finding algorithm. At each iteration of the algorithm, a voltage is chosen for the gate and the ion’s flight is simulated. Then, a metric is devised to evaluate the effectiveness of the gate. This metric, which differs for each gate design, is set to be positive if the ion is not stopped by the gate and negative if the ion is

stopped by the gate, in such a way that ions that are “almost” stopped receive a small positive score and ions that are “barely” stopped receive a small negative score. The root finding algorithm finds the voltage that results in a zero value of the metric. Adding a small amount of voltage to this root value gives the minimum voltage that results in the ion being stopped by the gate. This result can be extrapolated to all ions by taking the ratio between the minimum voltage and the ion’s energy. Multiplying any ion’s energy by this ratio then gives the voltage that must be applied to the gate to stop that ion.

For the mesh gate design, the expectation was that the voltage required to stop an ion would be greater than or equal to that ion’s energy. Since for a solid metal plate, the retardation potential would be exactly equal to the energy, the primary question was how the density of the mesh would impact the voltage to energy ratio. Therefore, the experiment was run for several different mesh opening sizes.

Figure 17: The trajectory of a charged particle (green) deflected by a mesh with 0.5cm openings and an ion energy of 0.5 simulated voltage units. The shown voltage is the lowest voltage that successfully stopped the ion.

For the mesh design, the metric for the root finding algorithm was based on the final x axis position of the ion. A negative value corresponds to an ion that ended up with a positive final x axis position, having been reflected by the electric field of the gate. A positive value corresponds to an ion with a negative final x axis position. The metric is zero at the location of the ion gate.

Figure 17 shows the results of running the simulated experiment for a mesh with physically plausible dimensions – 0.5mm wires and 0.5cm distances between wires. The particle energy was set at 0.5 simulated voltage units, that is, a charge of 1, a mass of 0.5, and a velocity of 1 along the x axis. The units of energy are directly comparable to the voltage output, which is

0.78 simulated voltage units. The energy ratio is then computed to be 1.56, which means that a voltage greater than the ion's energy must be applied to the gate to stop the ion. The ratio can be plotted for various mesh sizes, as in Figure 18 below.

Figure 18: The voltage to ion energy ratio for increasing mesh opening sizes, showing a quadratic trend.

The relationship between energy ratio and mesh size is well approximated by a quadratic relationship, with a mesh size of zero (a solid metal plate) corresponding to a ratio of 1 as expected. This experiment confirms the primary weakness of this gate design, as it means that a gate with large enough openings to result in a sufficient transmission ratio would necessarily require a high operating voltage. Ions with energies of 500eV would require at least 500V to stop, which would require a specialized high voltage switching power supply.

The same experiment was repeated for the deflection gate design. For this design, there are no questions regarding the optimal physical dimensions, as was the case with the size of the openings of the mesh. It is known that that the largest possible deflection plate area, placed as close as possible to the ion beam without interfering with it, will produce the strongest deflection effect, since the ion is affected by the field for the longest time. The experiment does not need to be repeated for changing physical dimensions, but the energy ratio must still be found.

The deflection box is modeled, and then a simulated ion's trajectory is computed. In this case, however, the metric for deflection success is more complicated. Because the goal of the deflection gate is to simply move the ion beam away from the Faraday cup, as described in the section on the deflection gate design, the ion does not need to be stopped inside the gate.

The metric is based on the position of the ion after crossing the 0.3m flight chamber and can be expressed as

$$m = \begin{cases} v_{\perp} \frac{l_{chamber}}{v_{\parallel}} - r, x_f > \frac{l_{gate}}{2} \\ x_f - \frac{l_{gate}}{2}, x_f \leq \frac{l_{gate}}{2} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where v_{\perp} and v_{\parallel} are the velocities of the ion perpendicular to and parallel to the axis of the beam, x_f is the final x -axis position of the ion, $l_{chamber} = 30\text{cm}$ is the length of the flight chamber, $l_{gate} = 3\text{cm}$ is the length of the ion gate, and $r = 1\text{cm}$ is the radius of the Faraday cup. The metric of Equation 10 is positive when the ion was deflected more than the radius of the Faraday cup at the far end of the flight chamber, and negative if it resulted in the ion being trapped in the gate or not being deflected away from the cup.

The experiment was run with a particle with an energy of 0.5 simulated voltage units.

Figure 19: The trajectory of a charged particle (green) with an energy of 0.5 simulated voltage units deflected by the ion gate. The shown voltage is the minimum required to deflect the particle 1cm by the time it reaches the far end of the flight chamber.

As shown in Figure 19, the applied voltage necessary to the deflect the ion sufficiently is small with respect to the energy of the ion. The voltage V shown in the figure is the voltage applied to each plate, so this means that a potential difference between the plates of 0.03 simulated voltage units was sufficient to deflect the ion away from the Faraday cup. The energy ratio of this gate design is then 0.06, meaning that an ion with an energy of 500eV would require 30V to deflect, which is a 94% increase in efficiency over the mesh design.

The experiment was also repeated for a different success metric, which measured whether the particle was fully contained by the ion gate. This meant that the metric was positive if the

final x position of the ion was greater than half the length of the gate, and negative if the final x position was inside the gate. The reason for imposing the stricter condition was to compare the behavior of the deflection gate design more directly to the mesh gate design, as the mesh gate design was based on entirely stopping the ions from moving beyond the area of the gate. If the deflection gate is also more efficient at fully blocking the beam, then it is unequivocally the better design.

Figure 20: The trajectory of a charged particle (green) with an energy of 0.5 simulated voltage units deflected by the ion gate. The shown voltage is the minimum required to fully stop the particle inside the box of the ion gate.

As shown in Figure 20, the minimum potential difference that stops an ion with an energy of 0.5 simulated voltage units is 0.22 simulated voltage units, which is an energy ratio of 44%. This energy ratio is, as expected, higher than the ratio for simply deflecting the beam, but is still significantly lower than the ratio for the mesh gate. Therefore, it can be conclusively shown that the deflection gate is the superior design choice.

The Beam Focusing Experiment

The second simulated experiment that was conducted sought to characterize the effects of the gate on the ion beam as the gate turns on and off, that is, while the potential on it is being raised or lowered. Though the capacitance, and therefore the time constant, of the gate is extremely small, it is nonetheless necessary to know how the gate interacts with the beam, and whether this results in a net focusing or defocusing effect. A focusing effect would cause the beam to become concentrated on the Faraday cup, and result in a momentary peak in detected current. A defocusing effect would do the opposite, causing a drop in current by deflecting ions away from the Faraday cup.

Figure 21: The transmission ratio (top) vs. voltage, and beam decoherence (bottom) vs. voltage for the mesh gate. The initial conditions for all the ions are the same for each voltage.

Running the beam focusing experiment on the model of the mesh gate showed interesting focusing behavior. Figure 21 shows the results of the simulation. At each voltage step, the trajectories of 30 ions with normally distributed energies around 0.5 simulated voltage units, and a finite beam size were computed. The top graph is the fraction of ions that made it past the gate for each voltage, as expected, there is an upward trend as the higher-energy particles pass through first, with the final value of 0.7 matching the theoretical prediction for three meshes with 90% of their area being free space (see Equation 7b). The bottom graph shows coherence distance, which is defined as the mean distance traveled in the direction perpendicular to the axis of the ion beam after passing through the gate. A high coherence distance corresponds to an unfocused beam. A pattern is seen: as particles first pass through on highly altered trajectories, and then are aligned to the direction of the ion beam again. As new particles begin to pass through the gate, the result is a coherence distance that fluctuates, reflecting the variability of the initial conditions of the particles.

For the deflection gate design, the beam focusing experiment produced results that were in line with theory.

Figure 22: The transmission ratio (top) vs. voltage, and beam decoherence (bottom) vs. voltage for the deflection gate. The initial conditions for all the ions are the same for each voltage.

At each voltage step, the trajectories of 20 ions with normally distributed energies around 0.2 simulated voltage units and a finite beam size were computed. The top graph is the fraction of ions that made it past the gate for each voltage. The increase in transmission fraction is roughly linear, except for a sharper increase around 0.075V, which corresponds approximately to the results of the operating voltage experiment, which showed that a voltage corresponding to 44% of the energy of the particle was required to fully stop the particle within the gate. Likewise, the approximately linear decrease in coherence distance reflects the particle beam being deflected less and less from the location of the Faraday cup. Taken together, the results of this simulation show that the gate does achieve a 100% transmission rate when open, and that as the voltage on the gate is lowered the ion beam is deflected less and less until it is focused onto the Faraday cup. Operating the deflection gate at a fraction of the voltage necessary to fully deflect the beam results in roughly that same fraction of the beam hitting the detector.

Designing the Physical Ion Gate

The modeling of the physical design of the gate was done in OnShape software⁵, which was also used to design the other components of the time-of-flight mass spectrometer. The deflection-based gate design was chosen for construction.

First, a material had to be chosen to make the main body of the box that houses the two parallel plates. After consultation with the Brown University Joint Engineering and Physics Instrument Shop, the best candidate was found to be 1.5mm-thick stainless steel square tubing. Having an existing square-shaped body for the box simplifies both the machining and the assembly process, as producing right-angle cuts is difficult. The tubing is cut to 3cm long, and the interior size of the square hole is 17mm on each side.

Figure 23: The square tubing that forms the body of the ion gate, with screw holes for assembly. Then, end caps were designed to fit over the open ends of the square tubing. These have a 1cm diameter hole that allows the ion beam to pass through. The end caps are attached by a screw on the top and bottom.

Figure 24: Two end caps, which fit onto the ends of the square pipe.

⁵ Available online at cad.onshape.com.

The deflection plates are likewise made from stainless steel. To fit inside the square tubing and not protrude over the screws which hold the end caps in place, and not be in electrical contact with the sides of the tubing, the plate is 25mm long and 15.5mm wide, which maximizes the plate's area within those constraints.

Figure 25: The deflection plate, with holes for screws.

To keep the deflection plates electrically insulated from the grounded square tubing, a two-part assembly system was developed. First, 3mm diameter holes were cut in the square tubing. Then, circular “T”-shaped pieces (Figure 27) were designed that fit within those holes and have their own internal 1.5mm hole for a screw to pass through. With one insulating piece on both the interior and exterior of the tubing, a screw can connect to the plate from the outside without electrically connecting the tubing to the plate. That same screw can also act as a connection point for a wire which can apply voltage to the plate.

Figure 26: A schematic side view of the deflector plate insulating assembly. The “Top” and “Bottom” insulator pieces are made of Teflon.

Figure 27: The Teflon “T”-shaped insulating piece, used for the “Top” and “Bottom” insulators.

Once assembled as shown in Figure 26, the plates are firmly held in place and the electrical connection is verified using a multimeter.

Two bracket pieces hold the gate in position at the location of the ion beam. Designing the brackets was a tradeoff between precision and adjustability. On one hand, it is useful to be able to calibrate the location of the gate to align it to the ion beam. On the other, too many potential axes of movement could make the gate difficult to install or necessitate frequent adjustment. The result was a compromise design, where the gate is held on either side by a stainless-steel bracket, which has screws on the top and bottom which act as a clamp on the square pipe. Tightening and loosening these screws moves the gate up and down along one axis, while it remains fixed in the other.

Figure 28: The brackets which hold the ion gate aligned. Note the four screw holes which allow movement along the z axis, while the y axis motion is constrained.

The entire ion optics assembly is mounted on four long parallel rods, which extend out past the last ion optics component to the location of the ion gate. Components referred to as “clips” clamp onto these rods, and in turn hold the ion optics in place. These clips are a standard part of the mass spectrometer and are used in three other locations.

Figure 29: Left – interior side of the clip, to which the brackets in Figure 28 are screwed. Right – exterior side of the clip. The clip clamps onto two rods, at the top and bottom.

The interior sides of the clips screw onto the brackets, meaning that the final assembly of the ion gate consists of joining three pieces: the left clip and bracket, the right clip and bracket, and the box. The final assembly is shown below.

Figure 30: The assembled model of the ion gate.

This design was finalized and then sent to the Joint Engineering and Physics Instrument Shop, where the pieces were manufactured. The gate was then cleaned and assembled in the laboratory and mounted onto the mass spectrometer.

Integrating the Ion Gate

Once the parts of the ion gate were manufactured, the gate underwent preparation, assembly, and integration into the mass spectrometer. Because the spectrometer requires a high-vacuum environment to function, all the manufactured parts needed to first be cleaned so as not to contaminate the vacuum. This was done by submerging the parts in soap water, acetone, and then isopropanol, each time placing the submerged parts into a sonicator to remove microscopic particulate impurities. The cleaned parts were then placed in an oven at 120°C to remove any residual water vapor. At this point, the gate parts were ready for assembly.

The assembly sequence for the gate was as follows. First, four of the “T”-shaped insulating pieces were placed into their holes on the inside of the square tubing. Then, the deflection plate was put on top of the insulating pieces, carefully aligning the screw holes on both. One at a time, insulating pieces were placed on the exterior of each hole, immediately after which a screw was put through the hole as shown in Figure 26. The deflection plate installation procedure was then repeated for the plate on the other side of the square tube. After these steps were complete, the ion gate looked as shown below in Figure 31.

Figure 31: Partially assembled ion gate, showing installed deflection plates.

Next, the two endpieces were screwed onto the square tubing, completing the box. Then, each bracket piece was screwed to the interior half of a clip. The exterior halves of the clip were then added, as were the clamping screws on the brackets. The box was then placed inside the two brackets, and the clamping screws tightened to hold it in place. Wires were connected to one of the screws connected to each deflection plate to provide electrical connections. This completed the assembly of the ion gate, its fully assembled form is shown in Figure 32.

Figure 32: Assembled ion gate (excluding wires) before integration on the mass spectrometer.

The assembled gate was then mounted onto the mass spectrometer. The vacuum chamber was pressurized, and the ion optics assembly removed. The ion gate was then added to the assembly, after the last ion optics component. This location is both convenient and necessary, as it requires the least disassembly to add the gate onto the spectrometer and places the gate directly before the flight chamber. The assembled ion optics with the gate added are shown below.

Figure 33: Ion optics assembly with the gate at the top.

The wires from the gate were then connected to the outputs from the vacuum chamber, and a multimeter was used to ensure that the connections were established properly. The assembly was then reinserted into the vacuum chamber for testing.

Testing the Ion Gate

The gate performed favorably when tested inside the mass spectrometer. A preliminary trial of the gate was conducted using a manually controlled voltage source attached to the ion gate. Sodium ions dissolved in water were used, and the potential difference between the extractor and the nanopore was slowly increased with the gate open until a current was detected at the Faraday cup. Then, the configuration of the ion optics was adjusted to find the optimal efficiency of the ion source – the efficiency is computed as the ratio of the current detected at the Faraday cup over the current detected at the nanopore ion source. Once optimal efficiency was found, the voltage of the gate itself was slowly raised in 5V increments to the voltage source’s maximum of 20V, then decreased incrementally to zero.

Figure 34 shows the current at the nanopore source and the current at the Faraday cup over a time range when the ion source is producing a stable beam of ions.

Figure 34: The current emitted by the nanopore ion source (blue) and the current detected at the Faraday cup (orange) over time during the first test of the ion gate. The ion gate voltage starts being raised at $t = 710$ s.

The energy of the sodium ions was 439eV, so the simulation predicts that a gate voltage of 27V would be sufficient to deflect the ion beam away from the Faraday cup. However, the voltage source used to control the gate in this trial was limited to 20V. No significant effect of the gate was seen until $t = 738$ s and 15V, where a dip in current at the Faraday cup was detected, corresponding to a dip in efficiency seen in Figure 35. At $t = 755$ s and 20V, the detected

current at the Faraday cup fell sharply, and the efficiency decreased to 32%. The efficiency and current stayed low until $t = 795\text{s}$, where the voltage was decreased to 15V again. Since the voltage applied to the gate was not sufficient to deflect the entire ion beam, the results of the experiment show the partial deflection of the ion beam away from the Faraday cup.

Figure 35: The efficiency (ratio of current at the source to current at the Faraday cup) over time during the first test of the ion gate. The ion gate voltage starts being raised at $t = 710\text{s}$.

The preliminary test of the ion gate showed that it is constructed properly, functions as intended, and succeeds at deflecting the ion beam away from the Faraday cup. A second trial was needed to show full deflection of the beam.

The experiment was repeated with a voltage source capable of producing a potential difference of up to 1kV. As in the first trial, sodium ions were used and the potential difference between the nanopore ion source and the extractor was increased until a steady ion beam was detected, in this trial the onset voltage was 480V. The potential on the ion gate was then increased in 5V increments between 0 and 30V, as the simulation predicted a voltage of 29V would be sufficient to close the gate. The potential was then increased from 30V to 125V to ensure that further increasing the potential on the gate would not cause unexpected behavior. Figure 36 shows the results of the second trial.

Figure 36: The current emitted by the nanopore ion source (blue) and the current detected at the Faraday cup (orange) over time during the second test of the ion gate. The ion gate voltage starts being raised at $t = 410$ s.

The second trial shows similar behavior to the first, with the current at the detector stepping down each time the voltage on the gate was increased. However, the current at the detector goes to zero when the gate voltage reaches 30V at $t = 530$ s. This confirms the accuracy of the simulation, as this voltage corresponds to the energy predicted as being necessary to close the gate. No anomalous current was detected when the gate voltage was increased to 125V at $t = 650$ s. The second trial unambiguously shows that the gate is capable of fully deflecting the beam at a voltage corresponding to 6% of the energy of the beam.

Summary and Conclusion

The results of the real-world tests of the deflection-based ion gate show that it is functional and well-suited for use in a time-of-flight mass spectrometer. Partial deflection of the ion beam was detected at a voltage corresponding to 4.5% of the energy of the beam. In a second trial, full deflection of the beam was observed at a voltage corresponding to the predicted 6% of the energy of the beam. Further simulations show that the gate does not interfere with the motion of the ions when open, and that as the voltage of the gate is lowered, the deflected beam of ions moves closer and closer to the Faraday cup. This behavior was observed during the real-world trial, where the voltage was insufficient to fully deflect the beam, but nonetheless a drop in detected current at the Faraday cup was observed.

Calculations and simulations show that the deflection-based design is superior to the mesh-based design. The time constant of the deflection-based design is extremely small, meaning that the gate responds quickly to changes in voltage, allowing it to open and close at nanosecond time scales. The gate is also compact enough to both fit within the design limitations of the mass spectrometer and to not introduce significant uncertainty in the length of the flight paths of the ions. Therefore, the gate can theoretically be used to measure masses as small as 10^{-27} kg, which is more than accurate enough to differentiate between bare ions and charged droplets.

The ion gate fulfills all the design requirements for use in the spectrometer. Further experiments will utilize it to verify that the nanopore ion source emits only bare ions and no charged droplets. If no droplets are found, then the nanopore ion source can be used as part of a novel method of protein sequencing, which relies on the ability to extract bare ions from the nanopore directly into vacuum. A method of protein sequencing based on this technique would have the potential to be more efficient with regards to the number of samples of a protein needed to sequence it and allow the sequencing of any length of protein. The availability of such a method of sequencing would be of tremendous benefit to the scientific community.

References

Alfaro, Javier Antonio, et al. “The Emerging Landscape of Single-Molecule Protein Sequencing Technologies.” *Nature Methods*, vol. 18, no. 6, June 2021, pp. 604–17. *DOI.org (Crossref)*, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-021-01143-1>.

Beynon, John Herbert. “Mass Spectrometry.” *Encyclopedia Britannica*, <https://www.britannica.com/science/mass-spectrometry>.

Drachman, Nicholas, et al. *A Nanopore Ion Source Delivers Single Amino Acid and Peptide Ions Directly into the Gas Phase*. preprint, Biophysics, 15 Aug. 2021. *DOI.org (Crossref)*, <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.08.15.456243>.

Gamero-Castaño, Manuel, and Albert Cisquilla-Serra. “Electrosprays of Highly Conducting Liquids: A Study of Droplet and Ion Emission Based on Retarding Potential and Time-of-Flight Spectrometry.” *Physical Review Fluids*, vol. 6, no. 1, Jan. 2021, p. 013701. *DOI.org (Crossref)*, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevFluids.6.013701>.

Koshland, Daniel. “Protein.” *Encyclopedia Britannica*, <https://www.britannica.com/science/protein>. Accessed 25 Apr. 2022.
“Mass Analyzer - Time of Flight.” *Physics LibreTexts*, 20 Apr. 2018, <https://phys.libretexts.org/@go/page/14604>.

Restrepo-Pérez, Laura, et al. “Paving the Way to Single-Molecule Protein Sequencing.” *Nature Nanotechnology*, vol. 13, no. 9, Sept. 2018, pp. 786–96. *DOI.org (Crossref)*, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41565-018-0236-6>.

Robertson, David. *Relaxation Methods for Partial Differential Equations: Applications to Electrostatics*. 8 Dec. 2010, <http://faculty.otterbein.edu/DRobertson/compsci/em-stud.pdf>.

Steen, Hanno, and Matthias Mann. "The Abc's (and Xyz's) of Peptide Sequencing." *Nature Reviews Molecular Cell Biology*, vol. 5, no. 9, Sept. 2004, pp. 699–711. *DOI.org (Crossref)*, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrm1468>.

Szumlas, Andrew W., et al. "Design and Construction of a Mechanically Simple, Interdigitated-Wire Ion Gate." *Review of Scientific Instruments*, vol. 76, no. 8, Aug. 2005, p. 086108. *DOI.org (Crossref)*, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2006308>.

Taflin, Daniel C., et al. "Electrified Droplet Fission and the Rayleigh Limit." *Langmuir*, vol. 5, no. 2, Mar. 1989, pp. 376–84. *DOI.org (Crossref)*, <https://doi.org/10.1021/la00086a016>.

Acknowledgements

I would like to first and foremost thank my advisor, Dr. Derek Stein, for letting me work on this project with him and for his advice and support throughout the process, and for letting me participate so fully in his lab group. Thank you as well to Nicholas Drachman and Brandon Pugno, who helped me understand the theory and assisted me in the experiments.

I would also like to acknowledge the physics faculty at Brown, especially those who have guided me and mentored me during my undergraduate education, Dr. Ian Dell'Antonio, Dr. Miquel Dorca, Dr. James Valles, and Dr. Anastasia Volovich in particular. Thank you, you have shown me the path forward as well as incredible kindness.

The physics community at Brown has been an incredible environment, and I am extremely thankful for all the friends I have made here, especially through the Physics Departmental Undergraduate Group. Thank you to my close friends Amber Fehrs, Hannah Joyce, Liam Storan, and Stacey Xiang for being there for me and always supporting me. And of course, to my parents Anton and Maria Furman, without whose support and encouragement nothing would be possible.

Appendix: Selected Code for Simulations

The Gauss-Seidel electric field solver, from `libem.py`.

```

@jit
def gs_3d(V, boundary_mask):
    """
    Computation step for the potential on a 3D lattice of points V.
    Parameters:
    - V, a 3D Numpy array of points at which to compute the potential
    - boundary_mask, a Numpy array of the same shape as V with 1s at lattice
      points containing solid structure.
    Returns the array V with computed voltages and dV, the largest difference
      between the old and new values.
    """
    dV = 0
    for point, v_old in np.ndenumerate(V):
        if (point[0] == 0 or point[1] == 0 or point[2] == 0) or \
            (point[0] == V.shape[0]-1 or point[1] == V.shape[1]-1 or \
             point[2] == V.shape[2]-1):
            # The point is on the boundary. Keep initial value.
            continue
        elif boundary_mask[point] == 0:
            # Ignore boundary conditions when computing
            i, j, k = point
            V[point] = (V[i+1,j,k] + V[i-1,j,k] +
                       V[i,j+1,k] + V[i,j-1,k] +
                       V[i,j,k+1] + V[i,j,k-1]) / 6

            dV = max(dV, abs(V[point] - v_old))
    return V, dV

```

Invoking the Gauss-Seidel electric field solver, from `libem.py`.

```
def compute(self, boundary_enfs, convergence_limit=1e-6, transient_ignore=100,
            maximum_iter=1e6, debug=False):
    """
    Compute the potential from boundary conditions.
    Parameters:
    - boundary_enfs list([callable]): a function which imposes boundary
      conditions given the simulation space.
    - convergence_limit: The step error dV that needs to be reached for the
      computation to stop.
    - transient_ignore: The minimum number of steps to compute.
    - maximum_iter: The maximum number of steps to compute.
    - debug: Whether to print a completion message with the number of steps
      taken.
    Returns the computed potential V.
    """
    self.find_object_masks(boundary_enfs)

    dV = 10 * convergence_limit
    transient = 0
    while (transient < transient_ignore or dV > convergence_limit) and
           transient < maximum_iter:
        for f in boundary_enfs:
            f(self)
        dV = self.gauss_seidel()
        transient += 1
    if debug:
        print("Computed in", transient, "iterations.")
    return self.V
```

Computing the electric field at a location in between lattice points, from `libem.py`.

```
def E_at(self, location):
    """
    Parameters:
    - location in simulation units.
    Returns the electric field at a given location in simulation units.
    """
    location = np.array(location)
    i, j, k = self.global_unit_to_point(location)
    if i <= 1 or j <= 1 or k <= 1 or \
        i >= self.point_space_size[0]-2 or j >= self.point_space_size[1]-2 or \
        k >= self.point_space_size[2]-2:
        # The particle is out of bounds. Return closest available point.
        i = min(max(i, 0), self.point_space_size[0]-1)
        j = min(max(j, 0), self.point_space_size[1]-1)
        k = min(max(k, 0), self.point_space_size[2]-1)
        return self.E[:,i,j,k]

    if np.linalg.norm(location - np.array(self.point_to_global_unit((i, j,
        k)))) < 1e-4:
        # The particle is immediately on top of a simulated point. Return
        value there.
        return self.E[:,i,j,k]

    E = np.zeros(3, float)

    # Compute the inverse distance weighted average of E field at nearby
    points.
    values = np.copy(self.E[:,i-1:i+2,j-1:j+2,k-1:k+2])
    close_points = np.indices(values.shape[1:]).astype(float)
    close_points[:, :, :] += np.array([i-1, j-1, k-1])
    close_locations = (close_points / self.scale) + self.top_left

    inv_distances = 1.0 / np.linalg.norm(location - close_locations[:, :, :],
        axis=3)

    values *= inv_distances

    return np.sum(values, axis=(1, 2, 3)) / np.sum(inv_distances)
```

The equation of motion for a particle, from `libem.py`.

```
def eom(self, t, y):
    """
    Equation of motion for the particle.
    Parameters:
    - t: time in simulation units.
    - y: [x, y, z, vx, vy, vz] in simulation units.
    Returns increment [vx, vy, vz, Fx, Fy, Fz] in simulation units.
    Applies gravity if it is specified.
    """
    x = np.array([y[0], y[1], y[2]])
    v = np.array([y[3], y[4], y[5]])
    F = ((self.charge / self.mass) * self.sim.E_at(x)) - self.gravity
    if self.track_force and not t in self.force:
        self.force[t] = F
    return np.ravel([v, F])
```

Excerpt from the equation motion solver in `libem.py`.

```
while total_time < t_span[1]:
    try:
        # Compute over the remaining time interval.
        p_res = ChargedParticle.compute_motion(self, (total_time, t_span[1]),
                                                stop_cond)

        time_partial.append(p_res.t)
        position_partial.append(np.array([p_res.y[0], p_res.y[1],
                                         p_res.y[2]]))
        velocity_partial.append(np.array([p_res.y[3], p_res.y[4],
                                         p_res.y[5]]))

        total_time = p_res.t[-1]
        if not self.bounce_velocity is None:
            # The particle bounced, set the initial conditions to the location
            # of the bounce.
            if self.bounce == 0:
                # The particle has ceased moving
                break
            else:
                self.initial_velocity = self.bounce_velocity
                self.initial_location = position_partial[-1][:,-1]
                self.num_bounces += 1
    except Exception as e:
        print("Exception occurred during time step", (total_time, t_span[1]),
              ":", e)
        break
```